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COMPETITION BETWEEN MANAGED AND WILD BEES

La competizione tra api allevate e api selvatiche

In recent years, concern has grown on a negative effect of managed bees (mainly honeybee and bumble bees) on wild bees. The negative effects could be exerted mainly in three ways: (1) competition for floral and nesting resources; honeybee colonies are larger than any wild social bee colony or solitary bee aggregations and can exert a competitive pressure on flower resources; (2) changes in plant communities, including the spread of exotic plants; in regions where managed bees are exotic, they preferentially forage on exotic plants implementing their reproductive success, with possible decline of native plants and disruption of plant-pollinator networks; (3) transmission of pathogens from managed to wild bees; the practice of transfer honeybees over long distances for crop pollination weakens the colonies and increases their potential to spread pathogens to wild bees. Literature revisions confirm (1), by more than half of the studies reporting a negative effect of managed bees on wild bees via competition for shared resources (MALLINGER *et al.*, 2017), especially when bees are outside of their native range (VALIDO *et al.*, 2019); but not (2), with only few negative effects of exotic managed bees on native plant communities. On (3), studies support negative effects via pathogen transmission, either within or outside native ranges of managed bees, but to a greater extent in the former. However, these studies just documented the presence of shared pathogens in populations of managed and wild bees, but do not show direct, long-term effects on wild bee populations.

The degree of competition strongly depends on landscape structure and resource availability: competition may be stronger in periods/contexts where

resources are scarce, such as dry seasons and homogeneous landscapes (HERBERTSSON *et al.*, 2016; ROPARS *et al.*, 2022), while in periods/contexts with abundant floral resources, managed and wild bees may be able to coexist. Moreover, positive effects of managed bees are recorded when they help restoration or conservation of native plants, which in turn benefit wild bees (CAYUELA *et al.*, 2011). In the case of managed honeybees, the density and the distance from apiaries can influence the degree of competition: effects are heavier above a density of 3,5 hives/km², and under 800 m of distance from managed hives, with reduced or no effects at increasing distances up to 1200 m, suggesting that the impact may be relatively local (HENRY & RODET, 2018). Another cause of variability is due to the species under concern. Many species and/or population traits can influence the result of competition with managed bees: oligolectic/polylectic habits, body size (influencing foraging range), sociality (linked to the duration of the species life cycle), size and status of the population (small and fragmented populations are at higher risk). Thus, although there is some general evidence of competition between honeybees and wild bees, few studies measured long-term or broad-scale wild bee populations fitness and survival.

How to assess the effects of competition is not an easy task. For understanding co-occurrence, species distribution models are often obtained by the contribution of environmental information (including weather variables and vegetation characteristics). Indirect competition is often investigated through pollen loads analyses, captured bee individuals or flower patches visitation, to obtain species association matrices (LÁZARO *et al.*, 2021). Niche overlap and partition of the network are also commonly adopted, together with the relation of wild bees' presence depending on the proximity and/or density of hives (SØRENSEN *et al.*, 2020). Other studies match floral resources at different scales, starting from the demand in terms of pollen/nectar, and on the combined availability of more than a resource. However, we still miss assessing the whole framework, not only focussing on available floral resources; competition should also consider a) the foraging success, since foraging could be disrupted independently by the availability of resources (i.e., by physical contrasts, or depletion of pollen/nectar of available but already visited flowers); b) the reproductive success, that may be linked not only to the feeding source but also to the nesting ones, as well as to the impact of parasite spillover; and finally, c) the longer-term population and community dynamics, a topic on which no data are available yet.

Notwithstanding scientific evidence on competition is still uncertain, risk management options need to be evaluated and actions should be foreseen by adopting the precautionary principle, particularly in or near areas with species of conservation concern (DG ENV, 2017). Where we face competi-

tion ascribable to severe changes in environmental conditions (intensive agriculture, farming and management practices, habitat disruption), mitigation measures could be fostered: improving habitats, supplying extra resources, adopting greener farming and management practices. Where we face competition resulting from the placement of managed bees as a response to an economic interest (pollination service, transhumance for honey production), we should implement the more appropriate restrictions which also take into account the benefits of providers and beneficiaries of these services. Guidelines that regulate the movement of managed bees across large regions should avoid the potential for pathogen introduction by a preventive screening of the stocks to be introduced; growers that use managed bees for pollination should limit the number of colonies and place them at maximum distances from natural habitats; bees used in greenhouse contexts must be prevented from escaping in nature. Very strict regulations (or even prohibitions) should be adopted in case of environments in which the managed bee are alien species; the reasons behind their introduction need to be carefully considered to obtain a social consensus over new forms of governance.

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